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Leveraging the Impact of Information Communication Technology (ICT) into Pedagogies of Religious and Library Studies in Federal College of Education, Abeokuta, Ogun State

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Abstract

Observation of trend has shown that ICT has not been effectively and adequately applied into the teaching of many subjects despite its applicability, it is against this backdrop that this paper investigates the leveraging the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the pedagogies of Religious and Library Studies in Federal College of Education, Abeokuta, Ogun State. One hundred (100) copies of a questionnaire were designed for 100 respondents purposely selected and used for the study. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and simple percentages. Findings revealed that thirty percent (30%) of the respondents strongly agreed that ICT tools significantly improve students' academic performance in Religious and Library Studies compared to traditional teaching methods in the study area, thirty-four percent (34%) of the respondents agreed with the statements, seventeen percent (17%) of the respondents disagreed, while the remaining nineteen percent (19%) strongly disagreed with the statements. The study, therefore, recommends among others that government and school owners should facilitate the enrolment of Christian Religious Knowledge teachers in ICT training programs to enhance their digital skills. Academic board planning should collaborate with curriculum planners to include interactive ICT-specific applications as integral components of the Religious and Library Studies.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Colleges, Religion, Leveraging, Library, Technology

Introduction

In recent times, there have been intense global campaigns for the introduction of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the teaching of Christian Religious Studies. It was on this basis that Al-Hawaj & Twizell (2008) observed that the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of most school subjects is critical to make learners learn better and teachers to teach well. It ensures transactional instructional communication where the teacher manages the human materials, time and space to make sure that instructional conditions help in drawing student's attention to stimulation and recall stimulus thereby improving performance (Balash, Yong & Bin-Abu, 2011; AlAmmary, 2012). No doubt ICT enables students to learn faster, remember longer, gain more accurate information and receive and understand delicate concepts. The use of ICT in schools includes computers, internet facilities, audio-visual devices, multimedia projectors, etc. Computers and Internet facilities are now in place in many institutions of learning.

It is envisaged that educators will see ICT as a major teaching and learning device across all educational institutions. Kosoko-Oyedeko & Tella (2009) have shown that with the power of interactivity and participation of multimedia and communication devices, the computer proves an excellent tool for the teaching and learning of school subjects. It has been found that Christian Religious Knowledge tends to be abstract in some situations and to remove the abstractness associated with the subject, the use of teaching aids or instructional materials in the form of information and communication technology is essential. Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are generally accepted as a modern instructional tool that enables educators to modify the teaching methods they use to increase students'

interest. Its general definition covers any product that will store, retrieve, manipulate, transmit or receive the information electronically in a digital form. It consists of hardware, software, networks and media for collections, storage, processing, transmission and presentation of information (voice, data, texts and images) (Jegade and Owolabi, 2003; Arinze, Okonkwo & Iwunor, 2012).

Statement of the Problem

Although, Information Communication Technology (ICT) has revolutionized all disciplines and all walks of life. A small percentage of schools in some countries especially in Nigeria have embedded ICT into the curriculum, and demonstrated high levels of effective and appropriate ICT use to support and transform teaching and learning across a wide range of subject areas. While many schools and colleges teachers are making use of ICT to improve their teaching; many still lack awareness about the available ICT tools suitable for instructional delivery. This is particularly true of the schools and colleges in Ogun State. It is against this backdrop that this study investigates the impact of Information Communication Technology (ICT) into the pedagogies of Christian Religious and Library Studies in Ogun State colleges.

Christian Religious Education

Christian Religious Education has emerged as a subject of prime importance in Nigerian schools. Its value in the school curriculum is unique among other subjects. The teaching of Christian Religious Knowledge in Primary schools in Nigeria can be dated back to the first half of the nineteenth century when the Christian missionaries established the first school in Badagry in 1842. This form of education spread to the North in the early 19th century and CRK was taught in the schools. At the early period, proprietors of schools were the Christian missionaries (Methodist, Church Missionary Society (CMS), and Roman Catholic who considered CRK as an important subject to be taught in schools. Since then, Christian Religious education has occupied a prominent position in Nigerian school curriculum till date. The view was asserted by Onovughe 2008. In recognition of the value attached to the subject was not only offered in the primary school alone but also in all levels of institution in Nigeria. Religious training and moral instruction were considered as fundamental to the development of sound education. The essence of teaching Christian religious education includes academic, moral; civil and spiritual objectives.

The Effect of Using ICT in Teaching Christian Religious Studies

Nowadays, schools or learning institutes provide computers and IT as the learning material to gain knowledge and experience. Students now have more understanding during the teaching process. The Internet especially provides many kinds of information and also learning tools in educational lines. The objective of the exercise is to prepare them in solving problems. One of the methods is by using multimedia activities. Besides learning, the teachers can attract the students' interest in the learning process and they understand more if they learn by using something that will attract their interest (Lubis, Embi. Yunus, & Wekke, 2009). Therefore, by implementing ICT technologies in the religious teaching process, it can improve the students' interest and also creative thinking. ICT plays some important roles which are to assist teachers in teaching, provide them with tools to illustrate some points or processes as well as to support long-distance educational system. On the part of the students, the importance of the ICT is to enable them to associate between concrete/ tangible facts from the abstract ones, to help promote the students' retention and to facilitate the Simulation and Recovery phases. To support the use of ICT, it is important to upgrade teacher's specialization and skill so that they may identify, troubleshoot and overcome various related problems. The School Resource Centre is one of the units within a school functioning in the collection, processing, managing and offering of various administration and educational resources tools. With the establishment of these centres, the goal to upgrade the teaching and learning process in reproducing knowledgeable community may be achieved.

ICT and The Library

Oyedun (2007) defines academic libraries as those libraries that are mainly found in tertiary institutions, they are established to support learning, teaching and research processes. Over the past twenty-seven

years, academic libraries have been affected by changes in information and communication technology. The rate of changes is still accelerating in this area. The introduction of various information technology (ICT) trends has led to reorganization, change in work patterns, and demand for new skills, job retraining and reclassification positions. Technological advancement of the past twenty-five years, such as the electronic database, online services, CD-ROMs and introduction of internet has radically transformed access to information. Rana (2009) opines that ICT holds the key to the success of modernizing information services. Applications of ICT are numerous but mainly it is used in converting the existing paper-print records in the entire process of storage, retrieval and dissemination.

According to the International Records Management Trust, it was observed that well managed records are a foundation for good library services; they serve both to document the policies, transactions and activities of library and to provide a trusted source of information to support decision-making and accountability. Many Library operations that traditionally depended on information derived from paper records have become partially or wholly automated. As library migrates to an on-line environment, records in electronic form are providing the basis for conducting business, serving the users, managing resources, measuring progress and outcomes, and protecting their own and others' rights. Records management is becoming increasingly dependent on technology. It is important therefore to have objective means of assessing the strengths and weaknesses of records systems and determining whether they are capable of capturing, maintaining and providing access to records over time.

Library is now more dependent on information in electronic systems to carry out their day-to-day functions and make decisions; common examples include systems designed for: Human resource management, online public access, Institutional repository, E-resources and Services, Registration, and Benefit delivery. New technology is making significant contributions to improving Library resources and services, achieving development goals and advancing e-library strategies. However, records management is not being given the attention it requires in the transition to the electronic environment. In too many cases, ICT systems are introduced without the essential processes and controls for the capture, long-term safeguarding and accessibility of electronic records. This undermines the ability of Library staff to trust the information generated by Library ICT systems (Rana, 2009).

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design aimed at describing and investigating descriptively how application of ICT can positively impact teaching and learning of Religious and Library Studies in schools and colleges in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population of this research are one hundred (100) respondents both male and female drawn from the Federal College of Education, Abeokuta, Ogun State. The choice of the students is because they are directly involved in learning process and they have relevant information.

Sampling Technique and Sample

The total sample chosen involves 100 students (male and female) from the in Federal College of Education, Abeokuta, Ogun State as the respondents to the questionnaire random sampling techniques was adopted in selecting the sample used. This type of sampling is very useful in this study because the researchers are studying the specific characteristics, features of the students.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used in the research was questionnaire 100 copies of questionnaire were administered on students of in Federal College of Education, Abeokuta, Ogun State. Copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and analysed using simple percentage.

Validation of the Instrument

By giving the drafted instrument to the senior colleagues and other experts to ascertain the items in the questionnaire, face and content validity of the instrument were done in the process of thorough examination of the instrument, changes were made by experts and senior colleagues in order to make the study relevant. The corrected copies of the questionnaire were adjudged suitable for the data collection, which make the instrument valid.

Method of Data Collection

To obtain valuable and reliable information from the respondents, one hundred (100) copies of questionnaire were distributed to them and collected immediately.

Data Analysis

All data were collected, interpreted and analysed in tabular form. Simple percentage method was adopted in analysing the numerical data.

Research Question One: What improvement can the use of ICT in teaching and learning of Religious and Library Studies make on the students' performance over conventional method?

Table 1: The Use of ICT in Teaching and Learning of Religious and Library Studies

S/N	ITEM	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Total
1	The use of ICT tools enhances the effectiveness of teaching Religious and Library Studies schools.	50	50	32	32	12	12	6	6	100
2	ICT-based instruction improves students' engagement and participation in Religious and Library Studies lessons	30	30	34	34	16	16	10	10	100
3	ICT tools significantly improve students' academic performance in Religious and Library Studies compared to traditional teaching methods.	30	30	40	40	14	14	16	16	100
4	The use of ICT-based lessons increases students' interest and participation in Religious and Library Studies compared to traditional classroom methods.	30	30	34	34	17	17	19	19	100
5	ICT-based resources and materials enhance students' comprehension of complex Religious and Library Studies topics significantly more than traditional textbooks and lectures.	36	36	34	34	18	18	12	12	100

Source: Field Survey March, 2024

The result in Table 1 above reveals the improvement that the use of ICT in teaching and learning of RE'LIBmake on the students' performance over the traditional approach. From the table it was revealed that 50% of the respondents strongly agreed, 32% agreed, 12% disagreed, while the remaining 6% strongly disagreed with the statement that the use of ICT tools enhances the effectiveness of teaching Religious and Library Studies in secondary schools. From the same table, 30% strongly agreed that ICT-

based instruction improves student engagement and participation in Religious and Library Studies classes, 34% respondents agreed, 16% respondents disagreed, while the remaining 10% strongly disagreed with the statement. Furthermore 30% of the respondents strongly agreed that ICT tools significantly improve students' academic performance in CRS compared to traditional teaching methods in the study area, 34% respondents agreed with the statements, 17% of the respondents disagreed, while the remaining 19% strongly disagreed with the statements.

From the Table 1, 30% of the respondents strongly agreed that the use of ICT-based lessons increases student interest and participation in RE'LIB compared to traditional classroom methods 34% respondents agreed with the statements, 17% respondents disagreed with the statement, while the remaining 19% strongly disagreed with the statements. Furthermore, 36% of the respondents strongly agreed that ICT-based resources and materials enhance students' comprehension of complex RE'LIB topics significantly more than traditional textbooks and lectures, 34% of the respondents agreed with the statement, 18% of the respondents disagreed with the statements, while the remaining 12% respondents strongly disagreed with the statements. These findings corroborated Owulu, Ntamu, & Monity (2016) who found that the utilization of ICT in teaching CRS as an instructional material has the potency of improving learning outcome of students' performance over the traditional approach.

Research Question Two: What are the factors militating against the teachers' use of ICT in teaching and learning of CRS in our schools and Colleges?

Table 2: Factors Militating against the Teachers' Use of ICT in Teaching and Learning of CRS

S/N	ITEM	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Total
1	Inadequate ICT facilities	49	49	30	30	11	11	10	10	100
2	Poor computer literacy of teachers	52	52	30	30	8	8	10	10	100
3	Problem of unstable power supply	46	46	30	30	10	10	14	14	100
4	Poor internet services	25	25	40	40	16	16	19	19	100
5	Inadequate funding of ICT programme	44	44	30	30	10	10	16	16	100

Source: Field Survey March, 2024

The result in the Table 2 above reveals the factors militating against the teachers' use of ICT in teaching and learning of CRS in our secondary schools. From the table it was revealed that 49% respondents strongly agreed, 30% agreed, 11% disagreed, while the remaining 10% strongly disagreed with the statement that Inadequate ICT facilities hinder the use of ICT in teaching and learning of CRS in the study area. From the same table, 52% strongly agreed that poor computer literacy of teachers hinder the use of ICT in teaching and learning of CRS in the study area, 30% respondents agreed, 8% respondents disagreed, while the remaining 10% strongly disagreed with the statement. Furthermore 46% of the respondents strongly agreed that problem of unstable power supply hinder the use of ICT in teaching and learning of CRS in the study area, 30% respondents agreed with the statements, 10% of the respondents disagreed, while the remaining 14% strongly disagreed with the statements.

From Table 2, 25% of the respondents strongly agreed that poor Internet services hinder the use of ICT in teaching and learning of CRS in the study area, 40% respondents agreed with the statements, 16% respondents disagreed with the statement, while the remaining 19% strongly disagreed with the statements. Furthermore, 44% of the respondents strongly agreed that inadequate funding of ICT programme hinder the use of ICT in teaching and learning of CRS in the study area, 30% of the respondents agreed with the statement, 10% respondent disagreed with the statements, while the remaining 16% respondents strongly disagreed with the statements.

Conclusion

The findings underscore the significant impact of ICT on teaching and learning, enhancing students' knowledge, understanding, and achievements. The use of ICT in CRS lessons not only facilitates comprehension of complex topics but also makes the learning process more engaging and effective. Furthermore, there is a consensus among respondents that ICT enhances teaching effectiveness, elevates students' academic performance, and fosters active engagement in CRS subjects. Educators are actively incorporating online resources, multimedia presentations, and collaborative activities into their teaching strategies, contributing to the positive outcomes observed.

However, persistent challenges, such as inadequate ICT infrastructure, limited teacher computer literacy, power supply issues, unreliable internet services, and funding constraints, hinder the full realization of ICT's potential in CRS education. Despite these challenges, the study highlights the transformative potential of ICT in CRS education, aligning with previous research indicating its ability to improve learning outcomes and teaching quality compared to traditional methods.

To fully harness the benefits of ICT in CRS education, addressing these challenges is essential. This will pave the way for a more dynamic and effective approach to teaching and learning in Christian Religious Studies within secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the study recommends that:

- i. Government and school owners should facilitate the enrolment of Christian Religious Knowledge teachers in ICT training programs to enhance their digital skills.
- ii. Government should promote training and support for software developers to create nationally applicable e-education software for teaching Christian Religious Knowledge teachers.
- iii. Academic board planning should collaborate with curriculum planners to include interactive ICT-specific applications as integral components of the Religious and Library Studies.
- iv. Government and school owners should provide and encourage the use of ICT tools in schools, particularly for subjects like Religious and Library Studies.
- v. Teachers should motivate and engage students to use ICT facilities for learning both inside and outside the school premises.
- vi. Government and school owners should establish functional ICT centres at all levels of education equipped with necessary resources and personnel to support effective teaching and learning.

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